

Technical report on narratives and images

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1. INTRODUCTION

This technical report examines the narratives and images of colonialism in school textbooks across three European countries. It is part of the EU Horizon project CONCILIARE —Confidently Changing Colonial Heritage— and represents the first task of Work Package 1. The aim of the Work Package is to understand the role of school textbooks in shaping shared ideas and emotions among young students about the cultural heritage of colonialism and fostering confidence in the future of Europe. More specifically, the first task focuses on the construction and transformation of colonial images and their emotive power in textbooks. The report explores colonial narratives and imagery in history, geography, religion, and mother tongue textbooks from 1950 onwards in Portugal, Italy, and Finland, employing a multimodal, data-driven perspective. This approach provides in-depth insights into the subtle and routine ways in which meanings and emotions tied to colonial heritage are constructed within the institutionalized school context.

This technical report presents the initial results on the narratives and images of colonialism in textbooks in the three countries, starting with providing wider perspective to the theoretical background and social psychological approaches to colonialism in textbooks.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. Textbooks and Colonialism

Schools play a pivotal role in the formation of identities and the political socialization of youth. Nation-states have particular interest in the education system, and textbooks are used to convey certain national representations and narratives to promote a sense of national belonging. Textbooks are state tools used to reinforce national narratives, myths, ideologies, symbols, and heroes, helping the state maintain control over its citizens by conveying a system of meaning (Sakki, 2014; 2016).

Textbooks are spaces where different kinds of knowledge—e.g., scientific, commonsensical, or ideological—co-exist side by side. They do not merely mediate brute facts or historical knowledge, but also symbols, opinions, attitudes, and tone (Crawford & Foster, 2008). The concept of collective memory, borrowed from French sociologist Maurice Halbwachs (1980), is vital to understanding the role of school textbooks in constructing representations and identities. Textbook knowledge is far more than factual information; it is always produced within specific social, cultural, political, and educational contexts to justify behaviors and actions designed to have specific social consequences (Crawford & Foster, 2008). In other words, textbooks aim both to transfer "objective" academic knowledge of the past and to construct social representations that draw upon emotions and memories important for group identity. Previous works on textbooks (e.g., Carretero et al., 2012; Crawford & Foster, 2008; Soysal & Schissler, 2005) emphasize the importance of schools and textbooks in the construction of a nation, national identity, and the divisions between ingroups and outgroups. In other words, textbooks can be seen as tools of identity politics and othering.

Research on colonialism in textbooks shown the strong Eurocentrism presented in European textbooks in countries like Belgium (Van Nieuwenhuysse, 2014, 2015), Italy (Leone & Mastrovito, 2010; Leone & Sarrica, 2012) and Portugal (Araújo & Maeso, 2015, Mendes & Valentim, 2012; Soares & Jesuino, 2003). Van Nieuwenhuysse and Valentim (2018) extended this research by: 1) not just focus on one national reality but on six former European colonizing countries –Belgium, Italy, England, France, Portugal and Spain; 2) adopting a diachronic perspective from the Second World War to the present day. The results showed a progressive evolution from apologetic nationalist accounts of colonialism to more neutral or even critical approaches engaging in multi-perspective mainly in France and Belgium. However, representations of the colonial past are, for the most part, still marked by “a covert (...) Eurocentric perspective that smacked of a certain Western triumphalism and superiority” (Wasserman, 2018, p. 267). The colonized are generally invisible, or represented as lacking agency, and the wrongdoings of the colonizers (i.e., the own national group) are almost absent in a kind of 'social amnesia' especially in Italy and Portugal (Leone & Mastrovito, 2010, p. 20; Valentim & Miguel, 2018). Overall, diachronic changes are found, but there is no widespread presence of material and discussions to counter the representations of Europeans as “bringers of civilization” (Turunen, 2020, p. 1019).

2.2. Social Psychological Approaches to Colonialism in Textbooks

The social representations approach (SRA), pioneered by social psychologist Serge Moscovici (1961), offers a framework for understanding how social knowledge, including narratives and images in textbooks, is socially constructed, maintained, and contested by individuals and groups in everyday life. Social representations are ‘ways of world making’ (Moscovici, 1988, p.231) and inherently political endeavours, influenced by the interests and actions of the groups producing them within specific intergroup contexts (Bauer & Gaskell, 2008). Power dynamics determine which representations are considered most credible or real, reflecting the dominance of certain groups’ representations over others. However, although social representations may seem stable or hegemonic, they still permit resistance, agency and change.

The ego–alter-object relationship forms the epistemological foundation of SRA (Moscovici, 1984; Marková, 2008). In SRA, knowledge is viewed not as an individual possession (a mental representation), but as something co-created through symbolic communication in social interactions (social representation). This means ego’s (e.g., “our”) understanding of the object (e.g., colonialism) is always shaped by the alter (e.g., “them”), and vice versa. Drawing on this interdependence between ego, alter, and object, the process of social re-presentation in textbooks is as much about constructing “us” (Ego) and “them” (Alter) as it is about colonialism itself (Object). These social categories are not merely positions from which we interpret social reality; they are embedded in a system of power relations that that gives some categories more power than others in defining and contesting this reality.

Previous research on textbooks highlights their role as tools of identity politics and othering, as they construct social representations that draw on images, emotions, and memories essential for group identity. This suggests that examining colonialism as a social representation allows us to explore how we perceive ourselves (“us”), view others (“them”), how we understand social and political reality in the past and in the future, and act within it. Social representations of colonialism

are thus inherently connected to social identities (such as ethnic, national, European, or global) and intergroup relations (e.g., between ethnic majorities and minorities).

This means that social representations of the colonial past and the colonial "other" are deeply intertwined with social identity concerns and intergroup dynamics. Othering, the process of categorizing groups as either superior "us" or inferior "others," has been closely connected to colonial discourses. As Edward Said explores in *Orientalism* (1978), colonial powers constructed the image of "the Other" to justify domination and exploitation. This process of Othering operates through cultural production, knowledge creation, and representation, reinforcing power imbalances by framing certain groups as different, inferior, or in need of control (Hall, 1997). Textbooks, as significant tools of socialization, often perpetuate these representations of otherness by depicting colonized peoples as exotic, primitive, or backward, thereby maintaining the dichotomy between the colonizer and the colonized. Similarly, Gustav Jahoda's (1999) work on *Images of Savages* shows that colonial era images of colonized peoples, often baldly dehumanizing, racist, and infantilizing, continue to circulate in subtle, unconscious, or sanitized forms in the contemporary Western world. For example, he claimed that representations of noble and ignoble savages continue to organize our thinking about ethnicity. Haslam (2006) theorized these types of images as dehumanizing. He distinguishes between two forms of dehumanization: mechanistic dehumanization, which likens people to machines devoid of agency, and animalistic dehumanization, which equates people to animals, denying them human attributes such as morality and refined emotions. Stripping groups of their human characteristics enables them to be perceived as less than human.

Two studies illustrate how media maintains images of Otherness by visually dehumanizing refugees. Chouliaraki and Stolic (2017) analyzed news images from five countries during the 2015 Syrian refugee crisis, identifying strategies such as massification, vilification, infantilization, marginalization, and aestheticization to portray refugees as a body-in-need, a helpless child, or a dangerous other. Similarly, Martikainen and Sakki (2021) identified six strategies in a Finnish newspaper to visually emphasize refugee otherness, including massification, separating, passivating, and demonization. Dehumanization was constructed through multiple means of visual expression. For instance, depicting masses of refugees, hiding refugees' faces, and using long shots stripped the refugees of individuality. Images of crowds of refugees gathering at the European borders; visual elements related to the military, police, and oppression (e.g., barbed wire); and the use of snapshots made refugees appear restless and threatening. Portrayals of refugees in shabby shelters and wearing dirty clothes as well as photos of border authorities wearing protective clothes and disinfecting border areas depicted refugees as dirty and uncivilized. Finally, images of helpless mothers and children featuring high viewing angles portrayed refugees deprived of agency (Martikainen & Sakki, 2021).

Following this line of work, the present project seeks to investigate images of colonialism and colonized people in the textbooks of three European countries.

3. THREE COUNTRIES

3.1. Portugal

Representations of Portuguese colonial history are influenced by luso-tropicalism, a theory disseminated after WWII to legitimize colonial actions. Since the 1950s, luso-tropicalism explains unique Portuguese relations with former Portuguese colonies, explained by a specific Portuguese character to adapt to the “tropics”. This character, according to luso-tropicalism, is also explained by the absence of racism among Portuguese individuals. Noteworthy, research shows that such luso-tropical beliefs, ironically, facilitate prejudice and racism in contemporary Portuguese society (Meuer, 2022; Valentim, 2011; Valentim & Heleno, 2018). By means of propaganda, propagation and diffusion along decades, luso-tropicalism transformed from a theory in the scientific domain to a hegemonic social representation in Portuguese society. Notably, ingroup serving, positive representations of a Portuguese colonial past were disseminated through media, but also via textbooks. Such developments led in recent years to a specific line of research, focusing on the analysis of textbooks and its representations of colonial history. In what follows, important work conducted by Araújo et al. (2013), Cabecinhas and Feijó (2010), and Valentim and Miguel (2018) will be introduced.

“Race and Africa in Portugal: a study on history textbooks” (Araújo et al., 2013) is a project that lasted from 2008 until 2012, with the aim of identifying Eurocentrism in Portuguese textbooks. By analyzing works from key stage 3 (age 12-15) results, among many others, show how African peoples are represented as “primitive” and “barbarian”. Results also indicate that Portuguese textbooks bring forward the idea of Europe being in the center of political organization. Furthermore, Portuguese atrocities are downplayed, and the development of concepts such as “race” is attributed to other colonial empires, but not the Portuguese. Similar results were found by Valentim and Miguel (2018), who studied textbooks and their development between the 1950s and 2000s. Here, content of colonial history before the carnation revolution (1974) clearly aligns with the dictatorial propaganda at that time, emphasizing a positive, ingroup serving tone. Shortly after the revolution, that nationalistic view seems to change a little, for example by not using first person plural (“We the Portuguese”) rhetoric. However, an absence of Portuguese atrocities remains, specifically focusing on development Europeans brought to Africa. Books from the 90s onwards show greater levels of anti-colonialism on the international level, however, little emphasis is still on atrocities and the exploitative nature of colonialism. Lastly, Cabecinhas and Feijó (2010) studied and compared which historical events are considered as most important in Portugal and Moçambique. Although both countries emphasize colonial past as significant national events, Mozambicans tended to focus, among other narratives, on the atrocities committed by the Portuguese, whereas Portuguese participants idealized the “voyages of discovery”. In sum, all studies show a positive, ingroup serving tone in colonial history narration. Cabecinhas and Feijó (2019) further show that colonial narratives differ, depending on the national context. In this research, we aim to further investigate such colonial representations, specifically focusing on colonial imagery in textbooks, a design unique to the Portuguese context.

3.2. Italy

The roots of Italian colonial history may be traced back to the 1880s, when the Kingdom of Italy began a process of territorial expansion in East Africa, focusing initially on Eritrea and Somalia, and then, starting in 1911, on Libya. This initial phase was marked by intense conflicts with the local populations: emblematic were the defeats suffered by the Italian forces at Dogali (1887) and Adua (1896) in Ethiopia, as well as the prolonged resistance of the Senussi in Libya, won only through the adoption of extremely repressive measures, including reprisals, mass deportations and the destruction of vital resources. In the domestic political context of these years, Italian colonial expansion met with significant parliamentary opposition, who denounced both its economic impact, seen as a waste of resources essential to national development, and its moral unacceptability. After the advent of the fascist regime, however, colonial activities acquired a new ideological and propagandistic centrality. Fascist imperial rhetoric tried to intertwine the myth of a "civilizing mission" with the urgent national demographic and economic needs. Fascist propaganda presented colonial expansion both as an historical mission, directly inherited from the Roman Empire, and as a source of civilization, since the Italian agricultural and working vocations were able to enhance the poor economy of colonized countries. By this propagandistic strategy, the Fascist regime aimed at presenting the colonial conquest only as a consequence of its current domination of Italy, putting into brackets the more remote origins of the Italian influence on a part of the African populations, due to the previous failed attempts of invasions. Interestingly, this communicative manipulation succeeded in such a way, that until now the historical narratives of colonial times are encapsulated in the social representation of Fascism, even in history manuals. One of the reasons for this selective forgetting of the first phase of colonial expansion may be linked to the dramatic salience of the war crimes committed in Africa under the direct responsibility of Mussolini. Beyond this propagandistic mask of civilization, in fact, during his attempts of invasion the Fascist regime was ruthlessly trying to build a so-called "Empire" to distract the attention from its growing difficulties. Military violent attacks culminated in the Second Italo-Ethiopian War (1935-1936), won only because the Italian Army, under explicit orders of Mussolini, extensively used chemical weapons, in violation of the 1925 Geneva Convention. This victory allowed to organize a massive propaganda campaign to celebrate the restoration of a colonial Empire, presented as directly linked to the old Roman one. After the collapse of the Fascist regime, this freshly renewed Italian "Empire" immediately collapsed too. Between 1931 and 1934, all colonial possessions in Africa and in Albania were lost, with the only exception of the Somalian protectorate, held by Italy until 1960.

These specificities of Italian colonial domination made it possible a "social amnesia" that until now covers up this period of the national past (Leone & Mastrovito, 2010). Until the work of history scholars proved without doubt the Italian colonial crimes (Labanca, 2004), a long-lasting social denial (Cohen, 2001) refused to admit that the Italian crimes in Ethiopia actually happened. From this moment on, the former literal denial has been replaced by a massive societal self-censorship (Bar-Tal, 2009), still marginalizing the awareness of this historical period from social representations of Italian past (Leone & Sarrica, 2017).

Moreover, a social myth depicting Italians as "good fellows" (*Italiani brava gente*) incapable of cruelty (Del Boca, 2005) widely influenced the social representation of Italian history, and seems to start to vanish from the social representations of the Italian past shared by young Italian people

only in the last decades. In fact, when presented in 2012 with a set of sentences describing, according to this social myth, the Italian soldiers as incapable of crimes, a sample of university students showed a modest – but not total – disagreement with the idea that Italians are good fellows in war (Leone & Sarrica, 2012).

There are therefore many reasons accounting for the “holes in memory” about Italian colonial times (Pivato, 2007), that seem not be spontaneously included in narratives about the national past, while on the contrary other troubled period of history (first of all Fascism) are vividly socially represented (Leone & Curigliano, 2009). Taking into account how much the awareness of the national historical past is fundamental to build a sense of civic belonging and engagement (Brusa, 2021), the role of school teaching on colonialism, and of historical teaching in particular, becomes therefore crucial (Brauch, Leone & Sarrica, 2019; Leone, 2017), and an in-depth analysis of textbooks, as relevant teaching tools, is in order.

Referring to this issue, a previous fine-grained analysis of seven important history textbooks addressing in 2010 the Italian students of upper secondary school showed how such a societal context influenced narratives on the Italian colonial past, textbooks remaining for the large majority of young generations the main source of knowledge about these historical events. In these books, the history of colonial violence appeared in fact overshadowed by the violence of Fascist regime. Moreover, as expected from the historical reasons already discussed, narratives on Italian colonialism were encapsulated in the chapters referring to Fascism. Finally, a clear and frank description of colonial crimes was used only by a minority of texts, while the other ones described Italian violence only vaguely (Leone & Mastrovito, 2010).

A subsequent more comprehensive study (Cajani, 2013), reviewing Italian history textbooks for upper secondary schools from the Fascist era to 2000, corroborated these less extensive observations that the myth of Italy's "benevolent" role in colonialism was slowly dissipating. Moreover, results of this important review showed an increasing acknowledgment of the war crimes committed by Italians both in their colonies and during World War II. However, the Author argued that Italian history textbooks seemed to continue to present a predominantly Eurocentric narrative. This means that the perspectives and experiences of colonized peoples during European domination, as well as their contemporary views on these events, remained largely absent from the historical accounts.

In the following research, we aim at adding to this previous body of data, exploring how images siding the narratives on Italian colonial past in textbooks used from 1950 till present days contribute to build up a visual imagination of this period, that is until now still self-censored in the general societal discourse.

3.3. Finland

Although Finland did not have overseas colonies, its involvement in European colonialism is complex. The concept of 'colonial complicity' suggests that Finland benefited economically from the broader colonial system despite not being a direct colonizer (Keskinen, 2019). Finland's historical ties to colonialism are also influenced by its past as part of the Kingdom of Sweden until 1809, and then the Russian Empire until 1917. This history, combined with the notion of 'Nordic

exceptionalism,' portrays Finland among other Nordic countries as detached from European colonialism, ignoring their indirect roles (Keskinen, 2019). Moreover, Finland participated in the colonization of Sápmi, the homeland of the indigenous Sámi people. Overall, colonialism is often seen as irrelevant to Finland's national history and is seldom discussed in contemporary settings, except in relation to other countries (Hakala et al., 2018).

Few previous studies have addressed colonialism in Finnish textbooks. Mikander (2016), for example, found that Finnish history, social studies, and geography textbooks portray the West as superior, often downplaying colonial violence while emphasizing Western achievements. Similarly, discussions about Nordic involvement in colonialism have frequently been excluded from history education (Mikander, 2015; Hakala et al., 2018). Kohvakka's (2022) study on colonialism in the Finnish history curriculum reveals that, while the underlying values of the National Curriculum promote understanding and respect for equality and diversity, the key content areas still emphasize Eurocentric historical narratives and do not explicitly mention any of the minority groups in Finland. Despite the ongoing influence of colonial legacies on modern societies and global migration, the curriculum neglects the history and enduring impacts of colonization. Kohvakka argues that, for instance, categorizing countries as "developed" and "developing" fosters a Eurocentric view that obscures the historical roots of global disparities, such as the transatlantic slave trade and the unequal distribution of wealth and power. This oversight not only presents an incomplete global perspective but also hinders students' understanding of the underlying causes of current political tensions and migration.

This study argues that examining colonialism in Finnish textbooks is crucial, as despite Finland's more indirect involvement in European colonialism, it still contributes to a broader history of European colonialism and power inequalities, which continues to shape migration, intergroup relations, and multicultural society today.

4. THE PRESENT STUDY

4.1. Portuguese Textbooks

Material

In a preliminary phase, 106 books about geography, history, math, mother tongue, and religion (1950s to present day) were scanned and inspected for content on colonial history. Those books which contained such content were selected for further analysis, leaving us with the following subjects: geography, history, mother tongue. Throughout the development of this research design, the decision was made to focus on imagery. Consequently, further scans were made, to find books that entail "colonial imagery". Certain books that were chosen at a first stage had to be excluded, as they did not contain the images to be analyzed in this research. A total amount of 20 books has been analyzed so far. Table 1 presents detailed information of the selected books and their publication years.

Table 1. Portuguese Textbook Sample

Field of textbook	Total amount of			Publication year
	Books	Pages	Visuals	
History	10	621	346	1957, 1975, 1981, 1985, 1985, 1996, 2006, 2013, 2021, 2022,
Geography	7	263	108	1954, 1958, 1980, 1987, 1992, 2013, 2022
Mother tongue	3	144	32	1973, 1995, 1997
Total	20	1028	485	

Method

Methodology on the analysis of images in the Portuguese context is inspired by the idea that space, time, and actors provide analytical dimensions to detect the structure of a historical narrative (Garske, 2015). Moreover, such an approach may also uncover what a historical narrative focuses on, thereby also, what it may neglect. This means that a focus on space, time, and actors makes visible a discourse that, to a certain degree, uncovers the power relations that exist within the historical narrative. Adding to that approach, we also focused on actions of the actors portrayed in every image. Moreover, we kept in mind that the function of an image always needs to be seen in relation to the text (Maier, 2004). This means that depending on the text, the meaning of an image can be completely changed. By considering in-text references of an image, as well as image captions, we came up with a category we describe as the “theme” of an image. To bring perspective, we also look at the origin of an image, if we can find such information. In sum, images in the textbooks are being categorized according to the following conditions: people (groups and actions), space, time, theme, and perspective.

Preliminary Results

Preliminary results on the categorization of colonial imagery in Portuguese textbooks will be presented. Data collection is ongoing, with additional images, particularly from geography and mother tongue subjects, currently being analyzed. The results include frequencies of image themes, time periods, perspective, depicted individuals, and actions.

Image Themes

Geography

Image themes on geography before the carnation revolution have a noticeable focus on the economy at that time (Fig. 1). Importantly to note, this focus on economy is very much based on the resources that are available in a specific country, reducing peoples and nations to an “economic value”. Books also mention the development specifically Portugal brings to the at that

time Portuguese colonies. Development in that case thematizes improvement of infrastructure in at that time Portuguese colonies.

Between 1975 and 1989, we still see a focus on economy. By using graphics and maps, books show trade routes and explain commercial relations between colonial powers. Notably, geography books after the carnation focus less on colonial history, wherefore less images can be found compared to before the revolution.

Books after 1990, of which some are still in use, do not focus so much on colonial history. However, they do depict maps showing how the Portuguese language is distributed on the globe, and thematize decolonization processes every now and then. However, we only have a total of 3 images, thus far.

Figure 1. Image themes on geography between 1950-2022

Figure 2. An example of colonial imagery from the 1950s can be found in a Portuguese geography textbook depicting a rice field in Guinea, then under Portuguese colonial rule. This is one of many instances in the book where local "resources" utilized by the Portuguese are highlighted. However, there is no acknowledgment of the exploitative nature of these practices. No mention of violence and forced labor.

History

In history, the majority of books between 1950 and 1974 thematize development, specifically based on infrastructural, maritime and scientific developments. Interestingly, we see development as a prominent focus also after the carnation revolution, however, based on a “different type of development”. In books between 1975 and 2022, the idea of development is more based on cartography, scientific, and maritime developments, and less so on infrastructure. We may interpret that the focus in more contemporary history books lies more on European developments, and less so on overseas.

Moreover, economy plays an important role in books after 1975, however, neglecting the exploitative nature of colonialism, but rather show commercial activities using maps and graphics. Moreover, images focus on slavery only in the newest books from 1990 onwards. Between 1990, and 2022, we see an increase in the number of images thematizing slavery. Few images on slavery are visible in the 90s. The number increases in two books we analyzed from 2021 and 2022 ($n = 13$). Figure 3. presents the themes in history books in more detail.

Figure 3. Image themes on history between 1950-2022

Mother Tongue

Colonial imagery in mother tongue books is less common (see Figure 4). For this reason, we did not find books for the period between 1975 and 1989, yet. Book collection is still ongoing.

Figure 4. Image themes on mother tongue between 1950-2022

However, findings are interesting, since we see how such books romanticize the idea of the Portuguese at sea (Figure 5). Focus lies very much on “voyages of discovery”, and how important Portuguese poets idealized that part of history. Instead of critically engaging with such an approach, the books that we found rather reproduce such a narrative, even in works from the most recent period (1990-2022).

Time zones

Geography

Between 1950 and 1974, notably the biggest sample for geography, we see 100% of the images focused on the 20th century (Fig. 6). This makes sense, since we found in the “themes” section that most images focus on “economic values” of at that time Portuguese colonies. Geography books before the revolution, therefore, focus on the present.

Figure 6. Image time zones on geography between 1950-2022

History

Looking at the time zones the images depict (Figure 7), we see a gap between 1950 and 2022. Books tend to focus on the 15th and 16th century. Then, we get the impression that books are being rather silent, and re-focus again shortly before during times of independence (see Figure 8). This tendency is visible in books between 1950 and 2022.

Figure 7. Image time zones on history between 1950-2022

Figure 8. An image thematizing independence of Guinea, Angola, and Moçambique in a history book from 2013.

Mother Tongue

The majority of the images depict poets or drawings with a maritime theme. In earlier imagery, there is a noticeable gap between the 15th and 19th centuries, while in newer imagery, the gap extends between the 15th and 20th centuries (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Image time zones on mother tongue between 1950-2022

Perspective

The perspective is determined by the origin of an image, or, if such information is unavailable, by the perspective conveyed in the accompanying text. It is evident that the selection of images in textbooks predominantly reflects a European viewpoint (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. The perspective in geography and history

We are continuing to investigate the concept of "perspective" in greater depth, with a particular focus on identifying the origins of non-European images (such as Figure 11).

Ligação de Nagasaki (Japão) a Macau.

Depois do estabelecimento definitivo dos portugueses como comerciantes e missionários, a chegada e partida de navios torna-se frequente:

Figure 11. An Image coded as a non-European perspective: Namban art from Japan

People

Geography

With regard to geography, we almost found no images about colonial history depicting people ($n = 11$). Few people can be seen in books before the revolution, for example farmers on plantations.

History

Figure 12 illustrates the distribution of "people" themes in history textbooks over time. History books from before the revolution often emphasize a colonial missionary narrative, portraying Christian figures as well as citizens, workers, navigators, and members of royalty. Interestingly, a shift occurs after the revolution, with a specific focus on the colonial war. Figures of resistance, such as Amílcar Cabral, represent one of the few perspectives that deviate from a Eurocentric viewpoint.

Figure 12. Distribution of “people” themes in history textbooks

Figure 13 provides an example of how locals (people) are depicted through their cultural practices (actions).

Figure 13. An image coded as “locals overseas” with the action of “cultural practices”, recreating a stereotypical imagery. The image also highlights an act of syncretism, in the text described as a “natural process”. (1996)

Mother Tongue

We do not find people so much in the mother tongue images ($n = 20$). Sometimes, images of poets are depicted. We also find human-like creatures based on certain legends, that people encountered when they were at sea.

People's Actions

or now, there is not enough data to make a distinction between subjects and the time periods. In Figure 14, we will see actions that correspond to the individual people depicted in images ($n = 154$).

Figure 14. Actions that correspond to the individual people depicted in images

Many of the images lack visible action ($n = 54$), as many are portraits. However, when actions are depicted, they often showcase the "cultural practices" of Indigenous people (see Figure 13 above), sometimes framed within the narrative of a civilizing mission. Images of exploitation are particularly prominent in books published before the revolution, portraying locals from overseas regions engaged in labor, such as working on plantations. Notably, these images omit any reference to the exploitative and violent nature of this work.

4.2. Italian Textbooks

Method

The study was conducted on school textbooks used in Italy from 1950 to the present day. Given the aim of the present study – to explore how images siding the narratives on Italian colonial past in textbooks used from 1950 till present days contribute to build up a visual imagination of this period still self-censored in the general societal discourse – in this first phase of this study we chose to focus on the examination of history and geography textbooks. Previous research already allowed us to appreciate how the history manuals that were used in Italy over a time span ranging from 1950 to 2000 increasingly acknowledged the war crimes committed by Italians both in their colonies and during World War II (Cajani, 2013). This review corroborated previous less extensive socio-psychological observations (Leone & Sarrica, 2012) suggesting that the self-serving myth picturing Italians as “good fellows” unable to commit war crimes was slowly dissipating. However, in the same research the Author argued that Italian history textbooks, slowly providing more realistic descriptions of shameful colonial events of the national colonial period, seemed to keep on presenting a predominantly Eurocentric narrative (Cajani, 2013).

This first phase of our work aims to grasp if and how images used in this period in history textbooks are contributing to this slow process of breaking the former denial or censorship on such a difficult knowledge about the national group. Moreover, we want to understand how geography textbooks could complement this advance in the building of a better historical awareness of students, when they elucidate the peculiarities of each territory and frame them in the evolution of the world.

To reach these aims, as first we selected the information necessary for the study by analyzing the paragraphs of history textbooks focusing on the Italian colonial period - typically included in the chapter concerning fascism - and the sections of geography textbooks describing the lands colonized by the Italians. In order to evaluate the evolution of representations of colonialism proposed in school textbooks from the 1950s to the present, the original time span of our books' collection was divided into eight decades (1950-1959; 1960-1969; 1970-1979; 1980-1989; 1990-1999; 2000-2009; 2010-2019; 2020-present day). For each of these decades, an attempt was made to identify 1 to 3 school textbooks used in Italian schools for both history and geography. A total of 33 textbooks were thus collected, including 21 history and 12 geography textbooks, divided into the eight decades as shown in Table 2 below. The selected texts are predominantly utilized in high school curricula; however, given the difficulty to retrieve geography texts exploring the topic of colonialism, some middle school textbooks were also included.

Then, following the collection and selection of the textbooks to be included in the sample, for each text the pages in which the topic of colonialism is addressed, as described above, were scanned. In this phase of the study, we focused on the images that accompany the narrative. Consequently, for each book, the images that accompany the narrative were identified. Accordingly, the sample comprises 55 images, 42 of which are found in history textbooks, and 13 in geography ones.

Table 2. Italian Textbook Sample

Years	History			Geography		
	Textbooks	Pages about colonialism	Images	Textbooks	Pages about colonialism	Images
1950-59	2	1	0	3	0	2
1960-69	2	4	0	1	6	1
1970-79	2	6	1	1	1	0
1980-89	3	10	2	1	4	2
1990-99	3	5	10	1	1	1
2000-09	3	9	8	1	2	3
2010-19	3	5	9	1	1	0
2020-present day	3	11	12	3	3	4
	21	51	42	12	18	13

Based on this collection, an excel database was constructed, in which the following information was recorded for each textbook: year of publication, publisher, title, authors, the number of pages dedicated to the topic of colonialism and the number of images included with the text. Each image in the text was then entered, accompanied by its title and caption, when applicable, and by the categories deemed useful for its analysis. To facilitate the qualitative analysis of the images, an *ad hoc* observation grid was constructed. This grid analyzed: (i) the *type of image*, categorized as follows: historical maps (all those maps that represent the African territory using the diction and division of territory of the colonial period, adding a specification on the presence or absence of indications on Italian and local troops' movements both on the Italian and Ethiopian fronts); modern maps (in which the modern diction and division of African territories is used); documentary photos; propaganda images; statues; drawings; newspaper covers and front page; (ii) A *concise description* of the image; (iii) the *historical period* depicted (the historical period to which the image refers); (iv) the time when the image was produced, if this information can be found; (v) *people*, categorized into the two main groups of colonized and colonizers, and more history's specific social groups as for instance Ascari, prominent political figures, etc.; (vi) *actions*, such as: violence and crimes, glorification; civilization, etc.; (vii) the *implicit message* conveyed by the image. After applying the observation grid for each of the selected images, results were organized into five main aggregations that better specify the general category "type of image": historical maps, documentary photos, propaganda, covers or front page of newspaper and/or magazine, artworks. Hence, for each type of image, relevant examples of each sub-categories were chosen and analyzed referring to observative notes coming from the grid that appeared to be suitable for commenting on the visual. For most of them, the observations that happened to be insightful were

especially people and action.

Results

The slow building up of a visual imagination of Italian colonial times

Results better detailed in the following pages suggest that images taken from history textbooks follow the general trend already described by Cajani's review of textbooks' verbal contents (2013). Also images siding the text, in fact, as time goes by seem slowly to give place to a more realistic representation of the Italian colonial period and of the severe violence against colonized people occurring in it. Interestingly, geography textbooks seem on the contrary to be still reluctant to include a consideration of Italian colonization in the overall description of countries involved in this violent intergroup relations.

Since what we are studying here is the long and difficult elaboration of a shameful historical past, it has to be stressed that also the absence of images is a relevant information to be taken into the due consideration. This difficulty to provide images to scaffold a visual imagination of Italian colonial times in geography textbooks is evident not only in the scarcity of images retrieved but also in the fact that sometimes these images lack any verbal capture or are incongruent with the verbal text that they are siding with. For instance, when in the decade 2000-2009 a geography textbook firstly gives a brief reference to the Italian invasion of Ethiopia (1936–1941), included within a broader discussion of African colonialism, the two images siding with the text show instead the transatlantic slave trade ($N=1$) or contemporary independence movements ($N=2$).

The evolution of history textbooks' images appears on the contrary more important and complex. The initial five sub-categories may be reduced, in this part of the data, to three main options: maps, documental photos and propaganda (being the newspapers' and magazines' images and the only artwork just another expression of Fascist propaganda). Starting from 1970, the use of images slowly yet constantly grows in these books over the decades, and the timing of this growing trend differs according to the diverse kind of images. Interestingly, both documentary photography and propaganda came late, as if more time was needed for supporting with more direct images of violences and manipulations the cruelties perpetrated in the Fascist era.

History textbooks

Analyzing the total sample of selected history textbooks, a key initial observation concerns the complete absence of images in the texts covering the two decades 1950–59 and 1960–69. While these texts address the theme of Italian colonialism in their written content, the sole exception is a 1950 textbook that entirely omits the topic. Similarly, one of the two textbooks from the 1970–79 decade and one from the 1980–89 decade also lack any images accompanying their discussion of Italian colonial history. Starting from the early 1980s, all selected textbooks include at least one image. From 1990 onwards, the number of images accompanying narratives on Italian colonialism experienced a significant increase.

The 42 images collected from the history textbooks can be categorized into several types: 15 documentary photographs, whether historical or contemporary; 14 historical maps; 8 propaganda

images; 4 newspaper and/or magazine covers or front pages; and 1 drawing (see Table 3). Among these, historical maps and documentary photographs are the most frequently used image types in the analyzed history textbooks. Examining the evolution of specific types of images over time, we note that historical maps are the sole type of image employed—when images are included at all—in textbooks from the 1950s to the late 1980s. Moreover, historical maps are the only type of image consistently used in every decade in which textbooks contain images, from the 1970s to the present. About a decade later, beginning in the 1990s, documentary photographs were added to the visual representation of Italian colonialism. Of particular interest is the fact that it is only from the 2000s onwards that history textbooks include explicitly propagandistic images, even though newspaper and magazine covers or front pages—used as early as the 1990s—can, in the specific context of our sample, be considered a distinct form of propaganda.

Table 3. Division of Images by Type and Decade in History Textbooks

Years	Historical map	Documentary photos	Propaganda	Covers of front page of newspapers/magazine	Artwork	Total
1950-59	-	-	-	-	-	0
1960-69	-	-	-	-	-	0
1970-79	1	-	-	-	-	1
1980-89	2	-	-	-	-	2
1990-99	2	5	-	2	1	10
2000-09	3	3	1	1	-	8
2010-19	3	3	2	1	-	9
2020-present day	3	4	5	-	-	12
Total	14	15	8	4	1	42

Historical Maps

The category of historical maps is particularly intriguing due to the specific characteristics of the maps included in this study. All these images have been classified as "historical maps" because they depict the nomenclature and territorial divisions of African lands characteristic of the colonial period (e.g., "Abyssinia," "Italian Somalia"), yet each map possesses unique features. All these maps highlight the territories colonized by Italians; some depict the entirety of Africa, others focus solely on the Horn of Africa with the areas colonized by Italy (Eritrea, Somalia, and Ethiopia), and a few additionally include Italy's location, from which the trajectories of Mussolini's expansionist goals are traced. Interestingly, only a small number of maps incorporate Albania and the Dodecanese area (including Corfu) among the territories targeted for Italian colonization.

Equally noteworthy is the inclusion—or absence—of Libya among the Italian colonies, with Libya often omitted in maps that focus on the Horn of Africa, where only Eritrea, Ethiopia, and Somalia are marked as Italian colonies, alongside the boundaries of Italian East Africa. Finally, some maps include the invasion routes of Italian troops, the fronts of Ethiopian resistance, and the territories held by Italy, Britain, and France in the region. Even when not explicitly mentioned in the legend, maps of the Horn of Africa often indicate the British and French territories, particularly the division of Somalia into three distinct possessions. Below is an example of a historical map (Fig. 15).

Documentary Photographs

A second important category of images used in history textbooks to accompany and represent the narrative of Italian colonialism is that of documentary photographs, whether they are historical photos from the colonial period or contemporary photos depicting the colonized territories at the time the textbook was published. They are predominantly photos that document the colonial period, with only two cases in which each historical photo is accompanied by a more modern one. The latter include a contemporary view of the city of Asmara in Eritrea and a photograph of a gas station built by Italians in the 1930s and still in use today. The photographic representation of a gas station constructed during the colonial period and still in operation, along with two photos showing bank buildings constructed by Italians in the colonies, falls within a series of documentary photographs ($N=3$) categorized as civilizing actions. Alongside these civilizing actions, the majority of the documentary photographs ($N=6$) depict violence and crimes committed by **Italian** troops in Ethiopia. This classification includes different types of crimes and acts of violence perpetrated by Italians against the Ethiopian population, such as executions, hangings, and even a photograph showing the bodies of Ethiopians killed during the Addis Ababa massacre, piled up to be burned. Following in frequency are three documentary photographs categorized as acts of glorification. All three depict the glorification of the birth of the Italian colonial empire, including the same photograph—presented twice—of Mussolini’s announcement of the birth of the Italian empire on May 9, 1936, in a crowded Piazza Venezia (Rome). This is followed by two photographs

of cityscapes of colonial towns (both during the colonial period and in contemporary times) and a single photograph capturing the historic moment when Haile Selassie, Emperor of Ethiopia, appealed to the League of Nations in Geneva, asking the international body to intervene against the Italian invasion. This photo is the only one of this kind and has been categorized as a denunciation of the invasion by the colonized.

When analyzing the individuals depicted in the documentary photographs, we observe a predominance of colonized peoples ($N=7$), mostly shown in photographs documenting episodes of violence or crimes they suffered. A smaller number of photographs depict colonizers ($N=3$), exclusively in moments of glorification, while the few depicting colonized people and colonizers together ($N=2$) only show scenes of violence and crimes. Below are examples of documentary photographs depicting the denunciation of the invasion by the colonized (Fig. 16), acts of glorification (Fig. 17), and the violence and crimes committed by Italian troops (Fig. 18).

Picture type: Documentary photos

People: Colonised

Actions: Denunciation of the invasion by the colonised

Figure 16. From the tribune of the League of Nations in Geneva, Ethiopia's negus Haile Selassie appeals to delegates for the international body to intervene against the Italian invasion.

Image type: Documentary photo

People: Colonists

Actions: Glorification

Figure 17. Piazza Venezia, 9 May 1936: Mussolini announces the birth of the Empire

Title: Episodes of the Ethiopian War, photographs of the time

Picture type: documentary photos

People: colonised and colonisers

Actions: Violence and crimes of Italian troops

Figure 18. The shooting of a group of Ethiopians, carried out in February 1937, when the actual war had been over for a few months. The invasion of Ethiopian territory was carried out quickly, and victory was achieved with ease due to the disproportion between the military technical resources of the two armies: just over 200,000 Abyssinians, armed with spears and rifles, had to face an army of 330,000 soldiers, 87,000 Ascari, 100,000 trained and equipped Italian workers, 350 planes, 250 tanks, 1100 cannons, 14,000 vehicles. The last Ethiopian army, commanded by Negus Haile Selassie, was defeated at Mai Ceu on 1 April 1936.

Examining the temporal evolution of documentary photographs (Table 4), it is noteworthy that images categorized as civilizing actions appear exclusively in the decade 1990–99, the same decade in which history textbooks begin to include images depicting violence and crimes committed by Italian troops. Interestingly, photographs categorized as acts of glorification only emerged in the late 2000s, coinciding with the decade (2000–09) during which the sole photograph depicting an act of denunciation by the colonized population against the Italian invasion is utilized. The two photographs of generic cityscapes, on the other hand, are both featured together in a single textbook published in 2012.

Table 4. Temporal Evolution of Documentary Photographs in History Textbooks

Classification of actions in documentary photos	n	Years
Civilization	3	1995 – 1995 – 1995
Violence and crime	6	1990 – 1990 – 2009 – 2012 – 2022 – 2022
Glorification	3	2009 – 2021 – 2022
Panoramas of colonial cities	2	2012 – 2012
Denunciation of the invasion by the colonized	1	2002
Total	15	

Propaganda

A third significant category of images found in the sample of history textbooks analyzed in this study consists of propaganda images, whose messages can be classified into three subcategories: propagandistic reactions to sanctions ($N=3$), glorification ($N=2$), and violence and crimes committed by Italian troops ($N=2$). The category of propagandistic reactions to sanctions includes a series of images opposing the sanctions imposed on Italy by the League of Nations in 1935. These images depict either Italy's strength and determination (such as a Roman warrior confronting a dragon symbolizing the sanctions or a tank of Italian products crushing the word "sanctions") or a more contemptuous response (such as a child seated on a toilet using toilet paper printed with the word "sanctions").

Propaganda of glorification celebrates the conquest of African territories and the establishment of the empire. One example is a comic strip published in the newspaper *L'Avventuriero*, which, using the emphatic language typical of the Fascist regime, glorifies the colonial conquest. The comic recounts the triumphant return of a colonizer to his beloved, who reminisces about their past as emigrants in America. The colonizer proudly proclaims that he has given Italians an empire, a people who will no longer need to "beg for bread." The comic concludes with the departure of new "migrants" aboard "magnificent ships" bound for the "new African provinces," called upon by Fascism to colonize (Fig. 19). This comic is the first propaganda image included in the sample, appearing in the decade 2000–09. Particularly notable are propaganda images classified under violence and crimes. These include the same image (Fig. 20), a satirical propaganda postcard created by Enrico De Seta for troops stationed in East Africa. This image, which appears twice in the sample, depicts an Italian soldier spraying gas at Ethiopians, described as "exterminated like ants" (as noted in the image caption), with the phrase "Armaments: here is the most appropriate weapon" written in the background. This image is present in the most recent textbooks. As these are propaganda images, the individuals depicted are primarily colonizers, except in the case of propaganda glorifying violence and justifying crimes, where colonized peoples are also shown as victims. Below are examples of propaganda images depicting glorification (Fig. 19), violence and crimes committed by Italian troops, and reactions to sanctions (Fig. 20).

Image type: Propaganda

People: Colonisers

Actions: Glorification

Figure 19. This panel taken from one of the first Italian comic strip newspapers, 'L'Avventuriero', is part of a story entitled 'Beyond the Ocean' and in the emphatic terms dear to the regime, prefigures the return from Africa of the victorious veterans and, above all, no longer forced to beg for the bread of foreigners

Image type: Propaganda

People: Colonised and colonised

Actions: Violence and crimes of Italian troops

Figure 20. Enrico De Seta, Satirical postcard for troops engaged in East Africa, 1935-1936

Image type: Propaganda

People: Colonisers

Actions: Propaganda reactions to sanctions

Figure 21. Propaganda postcard against sanctions, 1936

A Specific Case of Propaganda: Magazine Covers or Newspaper Front Pages

Within the sample of images analyzed, four covers or front pages of magazines and newspapers are included, which, due to their content, can be considered a specific type of propaganda image. These examples comprise propaganda of glorification ($N=2$), which also includes a representation of a battle won by Italy, and one example of propaganda portraying civilizing actions ($N=1$). The notable civilizing cover subtly suggests the progress brought to Africa by the arrival of Italians, depicting a plow held by two hands breaking the soil of the African continent (Fig. 22). Among the covers of glorification, one of particular significance is the front page of the newspaper *Gazzetta del Popolo*, which narrates the conquest of the empire with emphatic tones, announcing in its headline that "the empire reappears on Rome's fateful hills", *verbatim* quoting the declaration given to an enthusiastic crowd by Mussolini (the same that is depicted twice in the aggregation of documentary photos). Below are two examples of magazine covers and a newspaper front page.

Figure 22. The plough ploughs Africa 1942, cover 'Italian Africa

Image type: cover or front page of newspaper and/or magazine

People: no

Actions: Civilisation

Figure 23. No caption

Image type: cover or front page of newspaper and/or magazine

People: no

Actions: Glorification

Geography textbooks

The analysis of images included in geography textbooks, both for lower and upper secondary education, examined a total sample of 13 images—a significantly smaller number compared to those found in history textbooks ($N=42$). Consistent with the nature of the geography discipline, six of the thirteen images analyzed depict historical maps showing the boundaries and colonial divisions of Africa during the colonial period (see Table 5).

Table 5. Division of Images by Type and Decade in Geography Textbooks

Years	Historical map	Documentary photos	Propaganda	Covers of front page of newspapers/magazine	Drawings	Modern maps	Total
1950-59	2	-	-	-	-	-	2
1960-69	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
1970-79	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
1980-89	-	1	1	-	-	-	2
1990-99	1	-	-	-	-	-	1
2000-09	-	2	-	-	1	-	3
2010-19	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
2020-present day	1	1	-	-	1	1	4
	5	4	1	0	2	1	13

A temporal analysis of the images reveals either an absence or an extremely brief treatment of the colonial theme in the first three decades considered. For example, in the decade 1950–1959, there are two geographical maps of African boundaries during Fascist colonialism, which lack captions or accompanying textual context. For the first time, in the following decade (1960–1969), a historical map of the Horn of Africa appears with a caption (Fig. 24), although the contextualization remains brief. In contrast, no images related to African colonialism were identified in the decade 1970–1979.

Image type: Historical map

People: no

Actions: no

Figure 24. The Italian colonial empire at the beginning of World War II. The three maps show respectively: Libya (top left), the Italian Aegean Islands (bottom left), and Italian East Africa (right). For each territory is indicated the time period in which it belonged to Italy; and for the first positions acquired in East Africa the year of their acquisition.

Starting from the 1980s, images begin to include references to Italian colonialism, with a documentary photograph depicting Ethiopian independence movements and a Fascist propaganda image of the colonial empire in Africa. Interestingly, the latter image, within the "actions" category, was coded under the subcategory of "civilization," reflecting the propagandistic narrative of the time, which framed colonial conquest as a civilizing process for cultures considered tribal or archaic (Fig. 25).

A notable feature emerges in textbooks from the decade 2000–2009, where a brief reference to the Italian invasion of Ethiopia (1936–1941) is included within a broader discussion of African colonialism, accompanied by images that are not specific to that period. Instead, these images depict the transatlantic slave trade ($N=1$) or contemporary independence movements ($N=2$), a trend that continues in subsequent textbooks. For instance, in the period 2020–2024, African colonialism is represented by a historical map illustrating the borders of European colonies on the continent and a documentary photograph related to other cases of colonial domination, such as French rule in Algeria.

Despite the intrinsic connection between Italian and European colonialism in Africa and the perpetration of violence, crimes, and conflicts, the analysis of images in school textbooks reveals a striking underrepresentation of these aspects. Specifically, within the "actions" category and its related subcategories "violence/crimes" and "battle," only two images were identified. The sole image coded under the "battle" subcategory is a drawing from the early 20th century depicting the Battle of Adwa (1896). Similarly, the only image associated with the "violence/crimes" subcategory is a drawing portraying the sale of slaves around 1800. This scarcity of visual representations is particularly significant given that colonialism was fundamentally marked by systematic episodes of violence, exploitation, and armed conflict. These dimensions are therefore minimally represented in the educational materials analyzed.

Finally, a particularly significant aspect emerging from the analysis concerns the representation of "people" within the "type of image" category, specifically with regard to "documentary

photographs". It is interesting to note that the images in which individuals from colonized cultures are depicted are exclusively focused on the post-colonial period. Specifically, these photographs portray Eritreans, Ethiopians, and Algerians in contexts following the end of colonial domination ($N=3$).

4.3. Finnish Textbooks

Material

All history, religion, geography, and mother tongue textbooks located in Helsinki University's main library (Kaisa Library), having one of the largest collections of school textbooks in Finland, were manually reviewed from the 1950s to the present day. All textbooks containing something about colonialism or contained othering material were manually scanned. A metafile of 380 books was created, recording the number of pages and images and the general theme of the textbook. This resulted in thousands of pages and images, which needed to be narrowed down for analysis, given the limited resources and tight schedule. Based on the content of both the text and visuals, 1–3 books were selected from each subject for each decade, resulting in a total of 54 books for closer analysis. The selection was based on the visual assessment and content of the text. As a result, there were 54 books, with more than 1000 visuals (see Table 6 for more detailed information).

Table 6. Finnish Textbook Sample

Field of textbook	Total amount of			Publication year
	books	pages	visuals	
History	17	710	685	1950, 1957, 1965, 1966, 1970, 1979, 1980, 1988, 1992, 1994, 1996, 2000, 2005, 2008, 2011, 2016, 2016
Religious	14	148	109	1958, 1961, 1964, 1970, 1970, 1980, 1985, 1990, 2003, 2009, 2009, 2011, 2014
Geography	12	467	295	1954, 1955, 1960, 1967, 1970, 1972, 1983, 1998, 1999, 2001, 2005, 2016
Mother tongue	11	66	27	1952, 1963, 1968, 1970, 1979, 1981, 1989, 1992, 1998, 2000, 2000
Total	54	1391	1116	

The material was further narrowed down. Initial decision was made to include all those visuals that represented the African "other", either in the context of colonialism or something else. In addition, the visuals related to colonized "other" in the context of other countries were included, if these images or the framing text was related to colonialism. Furthermore, since the focus was on European colonialism, images portraying colonialism, for instance, from Asian perspective unless

directly related to European activities in the region, were not included. Following these criteria, in total 639 visuals were included for in-depth analysis.

Method

Multimodal approach to textbooks was operationalized by using visual rhetorical analysis (VRA) to scrutinize the content, form, and function of the images and surrounding texts through 3-phase analysis. These three phases were implemented using content analysis, compositional analysis, and sociosemiotic analysis. In the first phase, the content of the visual was scrutinized focusing on the people, actions, objects, and environment depicted in the images. During the second phase, the focus was on the form of the visuals: how relations were constructed in the image (power relations through viewing angle and framing, social distance, gaze, relative size of the elements), and how colors were used to communicate emotions and other messages (degrees of intensity, authenticity). The third phase focused on the function of the visuals, where the content and form were looked together, both within their immediate discursive context (surrounding text and the book), and within the broader societal and historical context (e.g., time of publishing). In addition to the visual, the caption and the text framing were scrutinized with the visuals.

During the first phase, the visuals were scrutinized and initially labelled either in “Us” or “Otherness” based on whether the image depicted agentic Europeans or Finns (“us”) or colonized others (“otherness”). This phase established the binary categories for analyzing how agency and identity were constructed through the visual content. In the second phase, visuals were further allocated in subcategories based on their commonalities of how the visual rhetoric (e.g., viewing angle, framing, distance) portrayed either “us” or “otherness”. During the third phase, the meanings of the images were interpreted in the context of colonialism, using the theoretical background of dehumanization (Haslam, 2006) and emotions as relational, embodied, and semiotic (Wetherell, 2012). As a result, “us” were represented and positioned in three ways: 1) conquerors; 2) civilizers; and 3) accountable. In contrast, from a European perspective, otherness was depicted as subjugated, crisis and hardship, joyful, empowered, dependent or incompetent, progressive, sorrowful, sexualized, and animalized. Furthermore, otherness was also depicted through landscapes or static elements such as buildings and statues. The visuals were allowed to be allocated in more than one category, since often the visuals deployed emotional narratives for both us and them.

Results

Narrative shifts in four school subjects

Exploring how colonialism is represented across various school subjects reveals some shifts in narrative emphasis over time. Older history textbooks framed explorations and colonialism through a predominantly Eurocentric lens, glorifying European endeavors and downplaying the experiences of colonized people. Over time, these narratives began to shift, incorporating themes of liberation movements, post-colonial challenges, and African perspectives.

Religious textbooks underwent a similar transformation. Early portrayals celebrated Finnish missionary work in Africa, while later editions began to address independence movements and

the resistance of colonized people. Geography textbooks also transformed: initially, they propagated Eurocentric perspectives and racial science, reinforcing hierarchies rooted in colonial thought. Over time, these narratives gave way to discussions on global development, disparities, and international cooperation. Mother Tongue textbooks reflected the sociocultural impacts of colonialism through stories and exercises, initially presenting colonial settings in a simplistic or romanticized manner. Over the years, these materials evolved to address themes of globalization and language evolution.

Together these gradual shifts across subjects indicate a broader trend toward more inclusive and nuanced representations of colonialism although challenges in fully deconstructing Eurocentric frameworks persist, as will be discussed below.

Images of Otherness

In total, there were 560 visuals depicting the colonized other. In 322 images the colonized other was represented as inferior and dependent, evoking a sense of powerlessness and reinforcing the narrative of colonized others as subjects to be pitied or controlled. In contrast, in 164 images the colonized other was presented as resistant, active, and in charge of their own future. Additionally, 74 images portrayed otherness through either landscape or static elements. In the following subsections, we present the distinct categories of representing otherness with example analysis and images.

The Figure 26 illustrates the representation of the colonized other within the Finnish educational context from the 1950s to the 2020s, displaying shifts in depiction across decades in school textbooks. The number of images in each category has been calculated relative to the total number of images from each time period (decade), allowing to focus on shifts in representations, rather than being influenced by the changing volume of visual material across the decades.

Figure 1. Representations of the Colonized 'Other' in Finnish School Textbooks (1950s–2020s)

Subjugated/exploited (111 visuals)

This group of images (such as Fig. 26) functions to present the colonial other as victim and as subordinate. The images are either candid shots, presenting enslaved, either being forced to work or being shipped overseas or maps presenting routes of trade of enslaved. Objects in the images, such as whips, chains, and lack of clothing, emphasize the subjugated position of the colonized other. In similar manner other visual choices, such as distance between viewer and the depicted subject, are used to strengthen the differences between the enslaved and the viewer: for instance, the enslaved are typically depicted in the images sideways, which creates a sense of detachment. The role of colonizers was often mitigated in the images, usually by not being included in the images or, for instance, discussing the role local tribal chiefs had in the trade of enslaved people. Images depicting segregation during apartheid are also allocated in this category due to the subordinate emotional state they convey.

Figure 26. Africans were transported from the interior to the coast and sold to Arab and European traders. Slaves were obtained through wars and raids between tribes and kings. Through the slave trade, weapons were brought to Africa, which were used in wars between tribes. (History 2008: Forum VI Cultural Encounters)

Content. The image presents a group of dark-skinned people, including women, men, and children, shown as enslaved. Among the group, one person is wearing "western" style clothing and a hat, while the rest are dressed in loincloths, with some children appearing to be naked. The group is walking in line, indicating captivity, with a few individuals chained around their necks. Two people are seen carrying baskets on their heads. One person is depicted holding an axe-like object on their shoulder and a rifle in their hand, while another is carrying a rifle and a wooden mallet, preparing to strike one of the enslaved. Objects present include rifles, a wooden mallet, baskets, and clothing, and the scene is set in an outdoor, open field environment.

Form. The image contains neutral contrast and bright colors, particularly red and yellow, using a simplified drawing style. The viewing angle avoids eye contact, creating an "offer" dynamic, with a slight high-angle perspective that gives the viewer a sense of power and emphasizes subordination. The individuals are shown in a sideways profile, creating a sense of detachment, with an oblique angle directed towards the enslaved group. The long shot and significant space around the figures convey impersonal relationships and strangeness. Colors within the image are connected, and a grass bench in the foreground acts as a frame, separating the viewer from the represented group. The line of figures moves towards the left, suggesting a left-to-right symbolic contrast of bad to good. Attention is drawn to the red clothing and the man holding a raised wooden club, as well as the person he appears to have struck or is about to strike.

Function. Cartoons provide a way to address an unpleasant historical period. Instead of depicting the trade of enslaved with a more realistic image, a simplified drawing offers a means to distance oneself from these events. Also, visual techniques create further detachment from the events (such as distance and an oblique angle). The image externalizes the role of Westerners in the trade of enslaved and colonialism, placing the attention on the dark-skinned slave traders. The image functions to depict the trade of enslaved while distancing the responsibility of white individuals for these events. The text surrounding the image reinforces this function, as the actions of the Portuguese on the African continent are described in a very neutral tone. In the depiction of Africans' reaction to the Europeans' arrival on the continent, it is noted that their own tribal chiefs justified that the Europeans (vumbi) had owned the land before them.

Crisis/hardship (88 visuals)

This group of images represents the colonial “other” through depictions of problems, conflicts, and crisis (Fig. 27). Commonalities in this group are the presence of violence (e.g., images of internal conflicts and uprisings), threat (e.g., emotional narrative, use of colors) and problems related to livelihood, living conditions and health issues (e.g., poverty, famine). Additionally, the group contains both diagrams and maps presenting challenges the colonized countries are facing in the modern era (for instance the development of GDP in developing countries and industrialized countries) as well as the problems resulting of colonialist actions (e.g., Rwandan Genocide, Apartheid, civil wars). Consequently, this set of visuals depicts colonialism as an ongoing continuum that persists today. Although some of these images could also be placed in the “Accountable Us” category, they lack the agentic European figure that would communicate a critique of colonialism.

Figure 27. Internal conflicts between different tribes in the Congo were brutal and bloody. (History 1998: Changing World - Industrializing Society)

Content. Three individuals are positioned in the foreground. Two of them are wearing military uniforms (and helmets) and are standing. The person in the middle is dressed as a civilian. All three appear to be adults. The person in the middle is being held by the wrist by one of the soldiers, while the other soldier appears to have lost the grip of the civilian. The trio is moving forward, the civilian seems to be stumbling and falling, reaching out with one hand toward the ground. The expressions on their faces are not visible. In the background, a crowd of people can be seen, along with what appear to be trees and buildings. There is at least one soldier in front of the crowd.

Form. The photograph is in sepia tones, having strong contrast and shadows. The viewing angle positions the viewer slightly above the represented. There is an oblique angle towards the soldiers and the crowd in the background, and the soldiers are sideways towards the viewer. This communicates detachment. The soldiers are moving leftwards, indicating a connection to the past/bad. The soldiers are above the person in the middle, thus appearing as authoritative figures. The civilian is depicted with a more frontal angle, suggesting an attempt to communicate attachment. The civilian is aiming towards forward/slight to the right, indicating hope and future. The trio is in the foreground, walking past the viewer (making the viewer as bystander). There are no frames between the trio and the viewer, and the distance between the viewer and represented creates social distance. The crowd in the background is separated from the situation by one soldier, enhancing the central focus on the scene in the foreground.

Function. The soldiers are walking and taking the civilian towards the left side of the image, which usually indicates something dab/past. In contrast, the civilian is trying to break free, being in more frontal angle

towards the viewer and aiming towards the right side of the image. This could communicate that the visual means function to create a connection between the civilian and the viewer, perhaps to feel empathy towards the civilian who tries to escape from the bad that is waiting him outside the image. The context of the picture is to visually depict the internal conflicts in Congo. Its function is to evoke various emotions such as tension, and horror (the soldiers are taking the civilian somewhere he does not want to go, and that is not revealed to the viewer). Additionally, its purpose is to demonstrate the suffering and disorder that prevailed in Congo at that time.

Everyday practices and spiritual otherness (62 images)

This category of images portrays local people and their everyday life, including both spiritual and secular aspects, representing the differences between the colonized other and us, without incorporating a value-based dimension (Fig. 28). These categories of images communicated joy, happiness, and contentment. The images in older textbooks were illustrations in black and white, portraying everyday life. The images in the more modern textbooks were depicted in bright colours, further emphasizing the positive emotions communicated through these images. Furthermore, the images are often close-up portraits or depictions of spirituality or community spirit. The colonized other is presented as equal with the viewer, using eye-level angle.

Figure 28. In West African Benin, Vodou is the official state religion. During the Zangbeto ritual, "night watchmen" made of straw spin energetically, and the ceremony culminates in the falling of the Zangbeto: inside is only a small fetish, a statue containing magical power. (Religion, 2011)

Content. In the image, there is a dark-skinned person leaning towards spiritual statue/totem ("night watchmen"). The dark-skinned man is wearing a patterned red and white skirt. A child is running in the background, wearing shorts and a shirt. The "night watchmen" is made of straw, and is bright blue, having red on top and brown straws in the bottom. In the background, there is a brick wall, and the ground is sand. The image is taken outdoors.

Form. The photograph is in bright, strong colours. The costume is in bright blue, red and brown, communicating joy. The background is tinted in warm orange tones, which usually communicate celebration, joy, and renewal. The dark-skinned man and "night watchmen" are filling almost the whole image; the "night watchmen" is in the middle, being the focal point. There is not much space between the represented and the viewer, and the image is taken in frontal angle and eye-level, indicating equality and connection. The colours continue in the background, indicating unity and collective belonging.

Function. The photograph captures the lively, exotic, and mysterious nature of the Zangbeto ritual in Benin, showcasing the large, colorful straw costume and the ceremonial actions of the participants. The function of the image is to portray the different spiritual habits the locals have, in a joyful manner.

Dependent/incompetent (45 visuals)

This category of images portrays the colonized other either as dependent of the colonial rule/Europeans, or as incompetent in relation to Europeans (Fig. 29). Some of these images were also allocated in the “Civilizers Us” category and contained images of missionary work. The commonalities within the visuals in this group are downward-looking angle, Europeans active role as the helpers, saviours, or the superior group and the use of framing that separates the colonized other from the Europeans. This group also contains elements of re-contextualization, since even though the image may have portrayed the colonized other as the active participant, the image caption or framing text depicts the colonized other as incompetent, with even the smallest progress attributed to the (previous) colonial rulers.

Figure 29. Prenatal care and maternity hospitals have reduced child mortality in developing countries (Geography 1999: School Geography Environment)

Content. The image features a fair-skinned elderly woman, possibly a nurse, wearing a white headscarf, a light-colored button-up shirt, and a buttoned skirt reminiscent of a nurse's outfit. She wears glasses and Western-style accessories. Next to her is a younger, darker-skinned woman dressed in an open floral shirt, holding a baby who is wrapped in a white sheet. Identifying the facial expressions of the individuals is challenging due to the angle or lighting. The fair-skinned woman stands close to the mother and baby, leaning in and gently holding the baby with her hands, while focusing her gaze on the infant. The mother cradles the baby in her arms, also looking at the child, with her shirt collar open, as if preparing to breastfeed. The baby appears to be gazing at the mother. The mother is seated on a bed with a poster or picture of plants displayed behind it. The setting is minimally furnished, emphasizing the simplicity of the space. The room's walls are made of corrugated metal, hinting at modest infrastructure. According to the provided context, the environment is a maternity clinic.

Form. The color photograph uses strong saturation to emphasize the contrast between the light colors of the caregiver and baby and the dark skin and clothing of the mother. The viewing angle places the Western woman looking downward at the darker-skinned mother and child, suggesting a power dynamic. The viewer also observes the scene from a high angle, conveying a sense of power or authority over the represented figures. Both adults direct their gaze toward the child, without making eye contact with each other, while the baby focuses on the dark-skinned woman, creating a connection between them. The

image's oblique angle positions both adults sideways to the viewer, but facing each other, highlighting the intimate moment centered on the child. The medium shot maintains a social distance, but there is noticeable space around the darker-skinned woman, hinting at a sense of detachment. The framing centers on the dark-skinned woman and child as the focal point, highlighting their connection. The adults' interaction is mediated solely through the child, with physical space between them indicating their differences, while the proximity between the child and the darker-skinned adult suggests an intimate bond and shared experiences.

Function. The dark-skinned woman is represented as receiver of interaction. She is depicted as needing help and lacking skills. Her clothing, colourful and vibrant, is in sharp contrast with the light-skinned woman's white attire (symbolizes purity and cleanliness). The light-skinned woman (apparently Western?) is portrayed as knowledgeable and as active subject. She is in a superior position in relation to the mother and child. The image is framing Western involvement in non-Western communities as inherently positive, necessary, and transformative. It implicitly suggests that without such intervention, non-Western societies would lack proper care and progress. The function of this image is to portray Western influence as compassionate and necessary. Simultaneously it maintains an underlying power dynamic that emphasizes dependency and the need for Western assistance. As such, the image is placed in two categories: 1) Otherness: dependent/incompetent and 2) Us: civilizing.

Empowered (47 visuals)

Images in this category serve to position the colonized other as an independent and sovereign actor through their emotional narrative. The category contains images of maps depicting the years of independence to represent colonized states gaining freedom, portraits of political figures (e.g., Nelson Mandela), and images of resistance and activism that demonstrates agency in the context of independence. The colonial other is represented as optimistic and equal to the viewer (Fig. 30). Other common features in this group include the type of images (colour photographs), equal viewing angles, and emotions of motivation, determination and confidence. Most images are vibrant, evoking feelings of joy and optimism.

Figure 30. A mural celebrating independence in the capital city of Namibia, Windhoek. (History 1992: Paths of Humanity)

Content. A light-skinned woman and a child next to a dark-skinned woman and a child. Both women are smiling, conveying a sense of happiness or contentment, and the children mirror this joy, reinforcing the overall cheerful atmosphere. The women are dressed in colourful, patterned clothing. All figures are

facing the viewer, engaging with direct eye contact. The women are holding their children, with one child carried in the arms and the other on the back. The background does not depict any specific environment, emphasizing the focus on the subjects themselves.

Form. The mural employs vibrant and bright colors, evoking joy, cheerfulness, and a hopeful vision for the future. The viewing angle is at eye level, suggesting a sense of equality, while eye contact between the figures and the viewer creates a direct and engaging demand for attention. The frontal angle enhances involvement, and both women are depicted on the same level, symbolizing equality between them. There is no central perspective, ensuring that all necessary elements of the image are revealed without hierarchy or dominance. The medium shot creates an intimate yet socially meaningful connection, with little space around the figures. This lack of space suggests connectedness, further reinforced by the absence of frames, which promotes a sense of intimacy and group identity. The arrangement places the light-skinned woman on the left and the dark-skinned woman on the right, subtly alluding to the passage from past to present.

Function. The mural celebrates diversity and unity. By depicting women of different skin tones together, holding children and smiling, it communicates harmony and togetherness. These feelings are further conveyed with the form of the image, where the elements communicate belongingness, equality and involvement. The lack of frames strengthens the feeling of unity, by communicating intimacy and group identity. The caption mentions "Independence celebration wall painting in the capital city of Namibia, Windhoek," which indicates the artwork was created to commemorate Namibia's independence, highlighting themes of cultural pride, and unity. Placing the light-skinned woman to the left side of the image might communicate that even though the independence was a result of mutual efforts, the locals are taking the charge in the future. This image transmits overall emotions of pride, joy, and happiness. Acknowledging the history, it expresses the positive power of working together towards a common goal and independence. Due to the emotional visual expression, the image is placed in the empowered otherness category.

Progressive (41 visuals)

Images in this category are divided into two types: pre-colonial images, such as cave paintings and maps showing advanced early cultures in Africa before colonial era, and representations of technological and societal progress since colonial times. Technological progress is portrayed through diagrams and images of local people adopting modern technology, while societal progress is illustrated through changes in, for instance, social structures. The content and visual means in these images convey an emotional narrative of progress and development that is independent of colonial rule (Fig. 31).

Figure 31. A community court at work in Rwanda in 2007. In the aftermath of the genocide, nearly 11,000 community courts have been established in Rwanda, employing about 250,000 lay judges. The role of the court is to judge the guilty but, above all, to clarify matters so the village can live with its past. Sentences are lenient, typically involving community service (History 2008: Forum IV – Cultural Encounters 2)

Content. There are six people in the image, four sitting behind a desk, one standing and one sitting on a bench their back towards the viewer. The four are facing the person sitting on the bench. The desk has green-yellow tablecloth (colours of Rwandan map). Behind the desk there is heavy curtain, having the colours of Rwandan map in it. The setting is indoors, but there are no other objects beside the bench, desk, and curtain. The facial expressions are not visible.

Form. There is neutral lighting in the image, and it seems to light the image evenly. The saturation and contrast seem to be balanced, although the curtain in the back seems to have higher exposure. The colours (on the tablecloth and curtain) are the colours from Rwandan flag, emphasizing the national identity instead of tribal identities. The image is captured from slight oblique angle since the perspective is not directly in front of the represented in the image. The sense of detachment is enhanced by the fact that the person sitting in the foreground has their back to the viewer, while the person next to them is turned sideways. Even though those sitting behind the desk are facing the viewer (creating a sense of involvement), their focus is on the person standing. Overall, the viewer is not participating in the image, but observes. The image is taken from medium to long distance, creating more impersonal than intimate relationship between the viewer and represented. Furthermore, there is space between the represented in the image, indicating that they are not part of the same group. The image is taken from eye-level angle, and since there is no direct eye-contact with the viewer, the image communicates offer. The focal point in the image is the interaction between the standing person and the group sitting behind the desk. The standing person draws attention, he is positioned in the left (past) and facing towards the right (the persons sitting behind the desk). The group of people behind the desk is looking at him, as well as the person sitting on the foreground.

Function. The image is, as mentioned in the caption, a scenery from a community court in Rwanda and the person standing is most likely a person who is on trial. The image portrays the Rwandan community as agents of their own justice, highlighting local, forward-looking solution and restorative progress instead of focusing on vengeance. Simultaneously the image communicates that the community approach the struggles on their own terms, and the lack of Western figures in the image emphasizes this. Overall, the image function to portray the colonized otherness as agentic and progressive, challenging the narrative of African societies as dependent on external intervention. Instead, the image communicates agency, self-determination, and capacity for reconciliation.

Sorrowful (28 visuals)

In this category of images, the colonized people are represented through depictions of misery. The images evoke emotions of pity, sorrow and empathy (Fig. 32). Most of the images illustrate poor living conditions or women at work, having their child on their back in baby wrap. In these images, the shots are candid, presenting the women from the side, not looking at the camera, while the child makes eye-contact with the viewer. Additionally, there are images where, instead of the child, the woman makes direct eye contact with the viewer, drawing attention to their conditions, while the child is curled up on their lap or crying, not looking at the camera. Most of the images are black-and-white photographs, which emphasizes the sorrowfulness.

Figure 32. No caption (Mother Tongue 1979: Language Skills)

Content. There are three people in the image: a woman, child and a person behind them. The woman is sitting on the ground. She is looking directly at the camera. Her posture is a bit slouched. She has some form of scarf around her, and due to the colours of the image it seems to be a bit dirty. She is having a child, who is wearing black, in her lap. The child is leaning towards the woman, and their feet is touching the ground. The child is looking downward and seems that eyes are closed. Their hands are in front of their mouth. On the background, there is at least one person sitting on the ground, looking at the camera. The environment is probably outdoors, but not much can be said about it.

Form. The image is a black and white photograph, having some tone of sepia. The image has dark and strong shadows, keeping the highlights in the background (which does not reveal anything). These choices emphasize the severity of the situation. The use of shading and dark highlights enhances the image's messy appearance, which communicates authenticity and evokes emotions related to anxiety and confusion. The woman is looking directly towards the viewer, presenting and demand, and woman's facial expression communicates sorrow, despair or weariness. Even though the image uses medium shot, presenting the woman above her knees, there is not much space around the persons in the image (being close shot). This indicates a close, intimate relationship between the viewer and represented. The woman is sideways towards the viewer, and thus the image has some level of detachment. However, the woman is looking directly at the camera, and the person behind her is facing directly the camera. As such, the image aims to create engagement with the viewer. The image uses high angle, indicating the viewer has the power over the represented people. The woman and the child are in in the middle and front of the image. Even though the gaze first focalizes on the woman, it quickly shifts from the person behind her to the child in her lap (being in the golden ratio). There is empty space between these represented, emphasizing intimacy and their belonging to the same group. The image is part of a full-

page collage and is located in the left corner. Thus, the placing indicates the current image is something that belongs to our culture. The other two images on the page are black and white alike (on the right a woman decorating Christmas tree and on the bottom sinking ship with refugees), and the second page of the spread contain an exercise, where the reader is asked to plan and write an essay based on the images.

Function. The image function to evoke emotions such as sorrow, pity, and empathy while looking at the colonized other. The direct eye-contact with the viewer and the close-up of the mother and child evoke intense emotions. Furthermore, the imagery of mother and child communicates vulnerability and loss, which further strengthens the narrative of sorrowful otherness.

Exotic (20 visuals)

The colonized other is represented in this group in a stereotypical and simplified manner (Fig. 33). These images function to maintain the dominance of the colonizers and contain elements of dehumanization (Haslam, 2006). Common features in this group include a lack of agency for the portrayed individuals, with framing text and caption often reinforcing the offensive content of the images, which is masked as exoticism. The images emphasize the differences between “us” and “them”. Most of the images in this group are from the early decades of textbooks, reflecting primitivism and racialization. These images are mostly black and white drawings or photographs.

Figure 33. The tropical forests of Africa and their inhabitants: A white man (88 kg) and two pygmies (each 65 kg) alongside a gorilla (330 kg) they have jointly brought down. (Geography 1955: Wide World)

Content. The image includes a white man, two indigenous people, and a gorilla. The European (?) man is dressed in stereotypical explorer clothing, having his rifle in front of him, while the indigenous people are wearing loin clothes and are holding spears. The Western man is looking at the indigenous people, while they are staring forward. The gorilla is holding its hand above its head. The image is in a jungle setting.

Form. The image is a black and white drawing. The viewing angle communicates equality between the represented and the viewer, unlike between the represented. The European man is looking downward the indigenous people, simultaneously smiling. This communicates dominance and control over the other represented. The indigenous people are perhaps taking eye-contact; however, their eyes are drawn in simplicity manner, and it is not clear whether they are presenting any demand or not. Their facial expressions are also unclear, although it seems they have their mouth tightly closed, and together with the eye browns, they seem a bit angry. The Western person is depicted more active through his gaze toward the indigenous people, and together with the frontal angle the viewer is invited to gaze at the indigenous people, presenting them as passive characters. The long distance emphasizes the impersonal feeling of the image. Even though the indigenous people stand close by the Western figure,

there is still space between them, indicating that there are differences between them and should not be viewed as similar.

Function. The image function to represent the colonized otherness in simplicity, stereotypical manner. The gaze of the Western man in the image guides the attention towards the indigenous people and the gorilla and emphasizes a hierarchy over the other represented. The viewer is invited to look at the indigenous people, and the minimal clothing and the absence of individual expressions or actions dehumanize them through exoticism.

Sexualized (18 visuals)

The colonized other is represented in this group as naked, containing dehumanizing elements. Most of the images depict more than one person; usually the naked colonized other alongside a clothed Western (European) individual, emphasizing the distinction between civilized Europeans and uncivilized others (Fig. 34). In addition, these images contain other visual means underlying the power relations and depicting the colonized other as inferior, such as composition, viewing angle and relative position of the individuals in the image. Most of the images are black and white, and the majority of the naked figures are female. A frontal angle is used in most of the images, placing the represented other “on display”. In contrast, in some images the oblique angle is used to further diminish the interpersonal connection and empathy, reinforcing objectification of the represented.

Figure 34. Finnish missionary work in the Ovamboland region of Namibia. Missionary Maria Wehanen is sitting next to King Kambonde III Kangula and his wife. (Religious 2009: In footsteps of Christianity)

Content. There is two women (one dark-skinned and one light-skinned) and one man (dark-skinned). The dark-skinned woman has some kind of clothing around her waist and jewelry on her neck, head, and wrists, but otherwise she is naked. The light-skinned woman is wearing a white shirt and a light-colored skirt, as well as a large hat. She has a necklace around her neck. The dark-skinned man is wearing a wide-brimmed hat, a vest, a jacket, and pants. All three people are sitting, side by side. They are looking slightly to their right. It seems they are aware of the photograph being taken and are posing for it. In the background, there are some trees/walls of trees, but it is unclear whether they are sitting in- or outside.

Form. The image is a black and white photograph, having some sepia toning. The image contains lots of shadows. The light seems to come from the left corner, and the hats create shadows on their wearers' faces. The light shines right towards the dark-skinned woman's face. The viewing angle is on eye-level,

creating equality between the represented and the viewer. The frontal angle creates involvement, which is emphasized by the medium shot distance and lack of space around the represented. Even though there is equality between the represented and the viewer, the dark-skinned woman is portrayed sitting lower than the dressed-up woman and man. This constructs a power relation between the represented, where the dark-skinned woman is positioned in lower position. The unequal relationship between the represented is further underlined through the framing of the image: the dark-skinned woman is on the left, which usually indicates the past, whereas the dressed-up represented are on the right, indicating future. Furthermore, the light-skinned woman is in the middle, and can be interpreted being the mediator between the past and future. Additionally, the dark-skinned man and light-skinned woman are sitting close to each other (holding hands), and there is no space between them (indicating they belong together). Moreover, there is space between the two women – communicating formality and detachment. The contrast in the clothing (one naked and two dressed-up) further emphasizes the differences between the represented.

Function. The image function to portray the dark-skinned woman as inferior compared both to the light-skinned woman, and the dark-skinned man. The clothing, or lack of clothing, is a deliberate way to emphasize the perceived divide between “us” and “them”. Those wearing clothes belong to the same world, symbolizing civilization and societal norms, and are visually detached from the reality where the dark-skinned woman lives. The contrast between the dark-skinned and light-skinned women strengthens the notion of cultural superiority. The clothing is used to communicate progress and civility, which further reinforces a Eurocentric perspective that equals nudity with primitiveness. Thus, the lack of clothing is used as a way to dehumanize the colonized other, and this image is in sexualized otherness category.

Animalized (13 visuals)

The colonized other is represented as inferior in these images. Comparisons to animals are made through metaphors, either in the images themselves or in the framing text. For instance, the text might equate the colonized other to a monkey or visually liken them to cattle (Fig. 35). This serves to reinforce hierarchies, positioning the colonized other as “less human” and thereby contributing to their dehumanization. The images most commonly employ a downward viewing angle to emphasize the dominant position of the viewer. However, an exaggerated low angle is also used to draw attention to specific details in the image. For instance, in the example image below, the focus is less on placard and more on the individuals climbing it.

Figure 35. Black slaves crammed into a ship on their way to America. In Africa, traders, often black tribal chiefs, periodically gathered slaves in port cities for the sea journey. Up to 80 percent of the slaves could die during the voyage, but the trade was still profitable. The first slaves were taken to Latin America around 1520 and to Anglo-Saxon Virginia only in 1620. The importation of slaves to America was banned in 1808, but smuggling persisted. (History 1965: History textbook for upper secondary school)

Content. Group of people (based on caption, enslaved). Facial expressions not clearly visible, most of the people are looking downward, hiding their faces, or looking directly to the camera. It seems they are wearing very little clothing. People are sitting very close to each other, in hunched positions. No movement is captured in the image. There are elements of ship equipment in the image: ropes, masts etc.

Form. The image is large, taking $\frac{1}{4}$ of the page. The image is from a frontal angle, indicating involvement (the image is part of our world). However, most of the people are sitting sideways to the viewer, creating detachment towards the enslaved. The image is taken from a high angle, indicating the viewer has power over the represented people. The image is also taken from long distance, emphasizing strangeness and impersonal relationship with the people in the image. The people in the front and middle are the most salient characters in the image. They are in the middle, in front of an empty space unfolding before people. There is almost an imaginary path, which leads the viewers eye towards the people crammed in the middle. Between the represented in the image, there is not much space between. This indicates that the represented belongs to the same group. However, there is empty space between the represented and the viewer, also due to the long-distance shot. This creates a contrast between the viewer and the represented.

Function. The picture's function is to depict the misery and conditions of enslaved ships. The image could have been placed either in the exploitation category or animalistic category. The image conveys a feeling for the viewer that the enslaved are treated as livestock, ripping their humanity. According to the caption, it does not matter that most of them die during the voyage, which communicates that they are perceived and treated as disposable objects. Due to the emotions evoked by the image, the image is categorized into the animalistic category.

Miscellaneous

Additionally, there were in total 74 images related to the colonized other without presenting activity or containing humans in the images. These visuals presented either nature or animals (usually as drawings) or buildings and statues, functioning as emphasizing cultural identity. These images do not contain a value-based dimension, but since they do not contain any activity, they are placed in a separate group.

European Us – the colonizers

In total, there were 200 visuals portraying Europeans as conquerors (102 visuals), civilizers (73), or taking critical stance towards colonialism and Europeans role (26 visuals). The “Civilizers” category had the most connections (26 images in total) to Finland, including images representing the missionary work conducted in Asia and Africa as well as images of the former President Martti Ahtisaari. The Figure 37 illustrates the representation of the European “us” within the Finnish educational context from the 1950s to the 2020s, displaying shifts in depiction across decades in school textbooks.

Figure 2. Representations of the European ‘Us’ in Finnish school textbooks (1950s–2020s)

Conquerors Us (102 visuals)

This group includes images of explorers, ships, navigation maps to new worlds, maps showing colonized areas (Fig. 36), and maps of routes used for transporting enslaved people. There are also images of battles, with the colonizers and their perspective as the focal point. The images featuring people are foremostly paintings that emphasize the superior role of the colonizers, or minimalistic portraits. These images function to legitimize colonial rule, presenting Europeans as strong and righteous figures while reinforcing hierarchies and power asymmetries between the groups. The framing text typically supports this narrative, for example, by using quotes from figures like Cecil Rhodes to portray an authentic voice to portray the British as the ruling race tasked with bringing civilization all over the globe. Most of these images were also categorized under the “Subjugated” category.

Figure 36. A map showing the main details of the Africa race. Examine the map's dates. In which decade does the acquisition of colonies in Africa appear to have been most active? The color denotes English seizures. The black arrow indicates French aspirations. (History 1966: Past Times Here and Elsewhere)

Content. There are no people in the image. The map contains black and red arrows, which indicate British and French conquests in Africa. A red explosion symbol on the map indicates struggles between France and Great Britain over parts of Africa. The image features a map of the African continent with the names of various European and African countries (the European country names indicate which African states were under which country's control).

Form. The image functions as an informative: there is no, for instance, direct gaze to establish interaction with the viewer since it is a map; instead, the communicative act relies on guiding viewers through visual symbols and text. The arrow and lines communicate a hierarchy of power dynamics. The perspective is given, and we are seeing everything that is perceived necessary. By depicting the whole continent, the map establishes a "remote" overview distance for analytical purpose.

Function. The function of this image is to visualize and clarify European colonial domination in Africa and their competition for control over colonies. The image function to present Western societies as conquerors. The image presents conceptual structure and shows territorial claims and expansion strategies without representing any dynamic narrative action. The image conveys relationships of dominance and control over regions during specific historical periods. The use of red and black indicates two competing colonial powers, emphasizing a sense of rivalry and urgency. The bold lines symbolize dominance and assertiveness. The lines and arrows guide the viewer's eye across the map. For example, the red line stretching from Cairo to Cape Town is dominant, emphasizing the British aspiration for a "Cape to Cairo" route. Additionally, the red explosion symbolizes conflicts and competition between European powers over parts of Africa.

Civilizers Us (72 visuals)

These images function to portray Europeans actions in colonized countries as civilizing, further establishing historical narratives of Great White Men and creating nationalist pride. By focusing on the "heroism" of colonizers, the agency of the colonized other is diminished, portraying them as needing to be saved (Fig. 37). As a result, most of these images are also placed in the Dependent/incompetent category. Most of these images are related to missionary work, portraying either key figures, baptisms, or maps showing the spread of missionary efforts.

Figure 37. Results from Southwestern Africa (Religious 1990: Anchor 5 – Church and religious in Finland)

Content. A light-skinned woman and a dark-skinned child, both smiling and appearing happy, dressed in white, western-style clothing, with the woman wearing sunglasses. The woman is holding the child, and the child also braces the woman, indicating mutual affection and comfort. The outdoor setting, with a visible sky and clouds, suggests a natural environment that contributes to a sense of openness and freedom.

Form. The image employs a limited color palette with a blurred background, creating a subtle effect with medium saturation and exposure. There is some level of shadowing, adding depth. The viewing angle is eye-level, suggesting equality between the viewer and the represented, and the frontal angle shows both figures slightly turned towards each other, reflecting a close relationship while inviting the viewer into their moment. The woman is looking at the child, offering warmth and care, while the child looks directly at the camera, creating a sense of connection with the viewer. The distance is close to medium, creating an intimate yet socially engaging connection, with minimal space around the figures. The framing centers the figures prominently, emphasizing their significance. The child is positioned on the left and the woman on the right, and the absence of framing elements fosters a sense of openness and invitation. The blurred background enhances the contrast, focusing attention on the subjects while lending a naturalistic, approachable feel.

Function. Although the child and the woman are on the same level in the image, the woman is holding the child in her lap, thus having some level of control and authority over them. The proximity between the woman and child suggests intimacy and care but function also to reinforce the hierarchical power dynamic wherein the European appears as a savior or caretaker for the African child. Furthermore, the woman's posture and smile, combined with the gaze towards the child, foster a narrative of kindness and moral superiority. This interaction can be interpreted as a message of "saving" or civilizing influence. The child, smiling and being comfortable in the lap of the woman, signal acceptance and gratitude. With direct eye-contact with the viewer, the child is actively reaching out to the viewer, suggesting a need for support and care. The gaze might also reinforce the perceived "necessity" of the white European intervention. The white, unifying clothing enforces the idea of missionaries as "saviors", with moral superiority and purity. The fact that both are wearing white, suggests a bond between the woman and child. White clothing on the child might also communicate that the child has been assimilated into the values of the woman's world: it detaches the child from what usually is seen as "traditional African clothing". Altogether, visual elements in this image function to glorify the role white Europeans had in Africa and simultaneously portray the colonized other as dependent.

Accountable Us (26 visuals)

There are few images that explicitly criticize colonial rule. However, many of these images in this group are illustrations rather than photographic or documentary-style representations, which can diminish their perceived credibility and historical impact (Fig. 38). This choice may distance viewers from the severity of the critique, as illustrations are often seen as interpretative rather than factual. While these images may simplify the topic of colonialism, their function is to condemn the actions of colonial powers. Although there are some images among the illustrated that hold colonial powers directly accountable for the hardships faced by colonies and the treatment of local populations, the effectiveness of this critique can be hindered by how the images are presented.

Figure 38. England's devilish hand envelops the globe. French cartoon from 1899. (Changing World: Industrialized society, 1988)

Content. The image contains a large, bony hand with long nails, the Earth and a Coat of Arms (resembles the UK's Coat of Arms). The large hand is emerging from the void of space and appears to grasp the Earth. Below the claw is placed the continent of Africa. The CoA is placed in the left corner of the image, and around it is a banner.

Form. The drawing is black and white, emphasizing the severity of the message in the image. The globe and the hand is taking most of the image, being the focal point of the image. The image does not have the traditional central perspective, which indicates that the image reveals everything that has been judged to be necessary. The Coat of Arm is on the left-upper corner, which can be perceived to reflect the past. The left upper corner has no shadows whereas the right-bottom corner is pitch black. This might indicate that the past has been bright (for UK?) but the dark corner on the right-bottom tells what reality is.

Function. The function of the image is to criticize the colonial rule and hold "us" accountable. Through the British Coat of Arm, the criticism is aimed towards United Kingdom. Africa is positioned under the hand, and Africa is explicitly written over the African content. Even though the choice of style (illustration) might diminish the severity of the topic, it still functions to open discussion of the accountability of colonial rulers.

5. DISCUSSION

Portuguese Textbooks

First results from Portuguese textbooks indicate, as expected and consistent with previous research, a shift in colonial narratives. In history textbooks, imagery before the carnation revolution (1974) serves a dictatorial ideology that positively represents a Portuguese ingroup, as previously indicated by Valentim & Miguel (2018). Such developments become clear when examining the specific themes that images focus on, as well as the people they depict—primarily Portuguese royals, Christians, navigators, soldiers, and citizens. In contemporary imagery, we find more photographs on processes of decolonization and the colonial war. Geography books from that period tend to focus on similar topics, however, also include enumerations of resources available in the colonies. Specifically, these books portray the regions still under Portuguese colonial rule as being largely reduced to their “economic value”. In contemporary works, content on colonialism decreases, as contemporary geography textbooks tend to focus more on the scientific aspects of geography. However, they also include content related to postcolonial imagery, such as “underdevelopment in third-world countries”. Books on Portuguese mother tongue, on the other hand, often emphasize the romanization of the Portuguese at sea.

Our results also demonstrate that the narration of colonial history has followed a consistent pattern since the 1950s, with perspectives largely remaining Eurocentric. The focus predominantly lies on the 15th, 16th, and 20th centuries, while the 17th, 18th, and 19th centuries receive less attention. This approach reduces overseas colonial history to a simplified narrative of a beginning and an end, perpetuating a European-centered perspective. These findings call for a greater emphasis on multiperspectivity in history teaching.

We argue that luso-tropicalism, as a dominant representation of colonial history, should also be addressed in teaching methods. Even in contemporary textbooks, the luso-tropical narrative—portraying colonialism in a positive and ingroup-serving light—is notably absent. Raising awareness of the role luso-tropicalism played during the Estado Novo in shaping historical narratives could foster a more comprehensive understanding of colonial representations and their enduring impact on contemporary perceptions.

Italian Textbooks

The latecomer among European colonizers, the Italians declared the birth of their “Empire” under the Fascist regime, which subjugated African populations with extreme violence. This violence was later denied for a long time and overshadowed by the social myth representing Italians as “good people” (Del Boca, 2005). After just a few years, the Second World War disrupted the domestic dominance of an already collapsing Fascist regime and brought an end to its fictive African Empire. With all Italian colonies, except Somalia, gaining independence through the peace treaties following the Second World War, “Italy did not experience the troubles of decolonization” (Cajani, 2013, p. 96).

Due to its very specific historical features, the colonial period could be expunged from the collective memory of the vast majority of Italians. This societal amnesia of colonialism (Leone & Mastrovito, 2010) persists to this day and is associated with the many “holes of memories” (Pivato, 2007) that characterize the lack of awareness of the most cruel aspects of the Fascist era, in which the scarce memories of the colonial period have been encapsulated. Framed by this still lasting societal silence on the colonial past (Leone & Sarrica, 2017), school teaching plays a more crucial role than ever in building awareness of the national historical past, on which a sense of civic belonging is constructed (Brusa, 2021).

To analyze how history textbooks contribute to enhancing this educational task of schools, an extensive review of Italian history textbooks between 1950 and 2000 was conducted (Cajani, 2013). The results showed that the myth of Italians as “good people” slowly dissipated, and textbooks gradually acknowledged war crimes committed by Italians both in their colonies and during World War II. Nevertheless, the author stressed that, beyond a growing self-criticism, Italian history textbooks continued to narrate colonialism according to a predominantly Eurocentric narrative.

The aim of the present Italian research was to complement these previous results by a fine-grained quantitative and qualitative exploration of images accompanying the texts narrating this historical period to Italian students. The evidence that emerged from the first phase of this research, which involved inspecting history and geography books, corroborates previous studies. Moreover, it shows that the gradually increasing number of images included in the pages of textbooks— especially historical ones—adds new nuances to our understanding of the complex socio-psychological processes that are gradually deconstructing the long-lasting silence on Italy’s colonial past. The absence of images in the first decades of the time span covered by the textbooks, as well as the different timing for the inclusion of documentary photos and later propaganda images (with media images from the Fascist period shown in the history textbooks as another instance of propagandistic manipulation), both suggest that the literal denial (Cohen, 2001) and subsequent self-censorship (Bar-Tal, 2017) characterizing the Italian societal discourse on the national period have influenced not only the presence or absence of images in textbooks but also the types of images used.

The more abstract representation shown by maps employs more implicit strategies of moral disengagement (Bandura *et al*, 1996). For instance, displaying a historical map of Africa where countries are distinguished by different colors according to the specific European nations controlling them suggests that the Italians engaged colonization activities similar to those of other countries.

The documentary photos, especially those depicting actions, implicitly reinforce the passivity of colonized people by portraying them as helpless victims. Interestingly, only one of the images collected in this first phase of this research on Italian textbooks shows the legal representative of Ethiopia raising his protest in front of the Society of Nations –a significant political action that led to the sanctioning of Italy.

Finally, propaganda images provide clear evidence of the extreme degree of moral disengagement that visual communication can reach, justifying the violence enacted against the colonized people. Interestingly, this last type of image is the most recent to emerge from the Italian

data collection on history textbooks. This can suggest that the temporal evolution described by this longitudinal study is closely tied to the renewal of generations. It implies that several generations are required to elaborate the more shameful aspects of an in-group past (Leone, 2018).

In spite of the many limitations of this first phase of research on Italian textbooks, some interesting insights for possible educational strategies have already emerged. For instance, the data suggest that images can be used not only as a complement to text, but also as stimuli to provoke classroom discussions, where these disengagement strategies may become evident. Moreover, when discrepancies arise between text and images, this can provide an opportunity to explore the meaning that could be attributed to this clash.

Finally, the absence of images illustrating important aspects of the national colonial past could also be used in teaching about a controversial historical period such as colonialism. In fact, this lack of images reflects the many difficulties faced during teaching, until the creation of a civic discourse can ultimately transform a former denial into a frank and realistic representation of the past. Since self-censorship (Bar-Tal, 2017) is widespread, the lack of images can be expected. This is yet another proof that images are a powerful tool to make evident a collective historical responsibility, especially when past victims are still marginalized in the current intergroup relations.

Finnish Textbooks

The findings from Finnish textbooks spanning the 1950s to the 2020s reveal persistent patterns of othering and dehumanization of the colonial other (Jahoda, 1999; Said, 1968), illustrating how textbooks contribute to the reproduction of colonial ideologies and power dynamics within educational settings (Hall, 1997).

The results show that colonialism is represented through visual and textual strategies that construct distinct categories for “us” (European colonizers) and “them” (colonized peoples). While earlier depictions overtly glorified colonial endeavors, more recent portrayals demonstrate a partial shift toward incorporating postcolonial perspectives and narratives of resistance. However, even these attempts often fail to disrupt the underlying Eurocentric framing of history.

The dominant ways of portraying “them” often depict the colonial other as either a victim and subordinate or through representations of problems, conflicts, and crises. Another common visual strategy shows local people in their everyday lives, capturing both spiritual and secular aspects that differentiate them from us. In contrast, “us,” the Europeans, are predominantly portrayed as conquerors, civilizers, or, more recently and less frequently, as critically reflecting on colonialism and their role in it.

As the visual rhetorical analysis (VRA) of Finnish textbooks on colonialism revealed, the choice of imagery is not innocent. Instead, visual strategies—such as viewing angles, framing, and compositional elements—are used to shape particular emotional narratives and reinforce power hierarchies. For instance, images from Finnish textbooks often depict colonized individuals in subjugated roles, such as in drawings of enslaved people being marched in chains. These

images, characterized by oblique angles and detached perspectives, create emotional distance between the viewer and the subject while reinforcing notions of powerlessness and dependency.

Similarly, the analysis identified visual strategies in Finnish textbooks that externalize responsibility for colonial atrocities, as seen in images where local leaders are depicted facilitating the trade of enslaved people or in images of violent postcolonial civil wars between African tribes, with European figures notably absent. These visual choices redirect focus away from European culpability, subtly legitimizing colonial systems. This approach echoes broader patterns of othering and dehumanization identified in media studies, where marginalized groups are often portrayed as "bodies in need" or objects of spectacle, perpetuating exclusionary dynamics (Martikainen & Sakki, 2021; Chouliaraki & Stolic, 2017). Such representations not only distort historical accountability but may also hinder the development of critical historical literacy among students.

Moreover, the findings demonstrate the enduring emotional and ideological power of colonial imagery. Rather than functioning as static presentations of the past, these visuals operate as dynamic tools for constructing intergroup relations and social identities. By positioning the colonized "other" as inferior or incapable, these images maintain historical hierarchies that inform contemporary perceptions of migration, global inequity, and cultural diversity. This study highlights how textbooks mediate intergroup relations by normalizing hegemonic narratives and power relations. This study suggests that visual rhetorical analysis (VRA) can be used as a methodology for uncovering and challenging these hegemonic portrayals of the racialized colonial "other."

The study suggests that VRA could be used in classroom teaching of colonialism to help students gain the critical visual literacy skills necessary to address the ongoing impact of colonialism and disrupt its emotional and psychological legacies. The study's implications also emphasize the need for educational reforms that critically address the biases inherent in textbook narratives and visuals. Revising content to incorporate diverse perspectives and contextualize colonialism's ongoing impacts is essential for fostering a more inclusive historical understanding (Kohvakka, 2022; Keskinen, 2019). By teaching students to critically analyze imagery, educators can equip them with the tools to deconstruct colonial narratives and develop a more nuanced, empathetic approach to history.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study explored representations of colonialism in three European countries—Portugal, Italy, and Finland—each with a different relationship to the history of colonialism. The project showed that the textbook representations share some common features, primarily rooted in Eurocentric narratives. In all three countries, colonialism was often depicted from the perspective of the colonizers, emphasizing their achievements and downplaying the violence and exploitation that characterized colonial rule.

However, each country also exhibited distinct patterns in its portrayal of colonialism. In Portugal, the luso-tropicalist narrative dominated textbooks and presented colonialism in a positive light, which in contemporary books was reflected in the focus on development and commercial activities. In Italy, the colonial past was long denied, with textbooks long time presenting Italians

as “good colonizers” before gradually starting to acknowledge the violence of their colonial history. In Finland, colonialism was depicted as a broader European phenomenon, often externalizing responsibility and omitting the nation’s involvement. Visual strategies, such as portraying colonized peoples as powerless or exotic, reinforced emotional distance and dehumanization.

Interestingly, we found more depictions of the colonial “other” in Finnish textbooks, despite Finland’s lack of a direct history of overseas colonization. Colonial history may be a more sensitive and silenced topic in countries with more difficult and direct colonial experiences, such as Italy and Portugal, while addressing the negative past is easier from a distance, especially when responsibility for it can be attributed to other European nations. Our results confirm the previous finding that textbooks are used to convey specific national narratives and serve as vehicles for identity politics. On the other hand, the fact that we found more dehumanizing imagery of the colonial “other” in Finnish textbooks suggests that the enduring roots of racism and white supremacy persist all over European societies. This means that, to understand present-day political tensions and intergroup relations, research on colonialism should not be limited to its impact on former European colonial powers, but should be expanded to encompass all European societies.

The consistent Eurocentric framing across the textbooks of three European nations highlights the need for critical reforms in educational materials, promoting multiperspectivity and fostering a more inclusive and accurate understanding of colonialism’s legacy. By integrating diverse perspectives and confronting historical wrongdoings and injustices, textbooks can contribute to a more equitable and critically engaged society.

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The report is designed to meet the consortium academic and technical needs.

